
Status of Job Opportunities in Librarianship: A Comparative Study of Four Indian States

Mr. Umesh A. Khadse¹ & Dr. Harshal Nimbhorkar²

¹Research Scholar, P.G. Teaching Department of Library and Information Science,
Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati

²Librarian, Narayanrao Rana Mahavidyalaya, Badnera, Amravati
Corresponding Author - Mr. Umesh A. Khadse

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Abstract:

The present study aims to identify and assess the job opportunities for the professionally qualified LIS professionals in the area of Library and Information Science. The data required to carry out the study have been collected from 'Employment News', 'University News' and 'LIS Link'. The data collected have been represented through tables and figures. The data collected have been analysed to reflect the different aspects of LIS Profession in different states of India such as Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka and Gujrat. The preliminary data was collected from this source during the year 2012 to 2017. The study puts forwarded some suggestions to ensure employability of LIS Professionals in India showing state wise job opportunities and employment. However, the same research work can be carried out on a large scale to have a generalised conclusion highlighting the scenario of job opportunity and output of LIS professionals in the Indian context.

Keyword: LIS Education, LIS Jobs, University News, Employment News, LIS Links.

Introduction:

Library and Information Science discipline is a multidisciplinary study area that deals with the in-depth study of information selection, acquisition, organization, dissemination and storage. Sinha and Pandey (2014) are of the view that librarianship is a growing field which has by now attained the status of a separate discipline in the universe of knowledge. Ameen and Wraich (2011) noted that LIS education is to develop competent and skilled human resources to meet the changing needs of digital environment. Changes at work place in a digital/virtual environment have compelled library and information professionals to reorient

themselves and compete in the global market as well.

Library & Information Science (LIS) courses have lot of potential to develop the knowledge and skills required to sustain and survive in the present-day knowledge society. Globalization and liberalization have opened up multiple career options to the LIS professionals. The traditional roles of LIS have changed with the advances in Information and Communication Technologies. LIS professionals are expected to be academics of higher order with competence to work in a hypertext, networked, digital environment. Hence, the LIS education should impart the learners, the necessary skills to gain employment upon

graduation and to develop the vision and understanding to help them cope better with the rapidly changing world.

Now days, a number of career prospects are available in Library and Information Science. The qualified and trained professionals are employed in various libraries and information Centres. LIS professionals can select the type of library as per their own interest. Thus, there is a very bright future prospect for LIS professional. And only the trained personnel in LIS can have employment opportunities in the various sectors.

Employability according to Knight and Yorke (2004) refers to capability of getting and keeping satisfactory work, getting work from somebody for pay or state of being employed. It can be defined as “a set of achievements skills, understandings and personal attributes that makes graduates more likely to gain employment and be successful in their chosen occupations, which benefits themselves, the workforce, the community and the economy.” In the same vein Robinson (2000) opines that employability are those basic skills necessary for getting, keeping, and doing well on a job. The skills are teachable skills which are in three categories: basic academic skills, higher-order thinking skills and personal qualities.

It is therefore imperative that employment aspirants have to meet the employers' expectations to get an opportunity to work in a particular environment. In

addition to this, knowledge, techniques, skills, abilities, values, aspirations, wants, needs, dreams and personal style of a candidate seeking employment also enhance the candidate's employability. (Tadasad, 2015)

Objectives of the study

- To find out the job advertisement trends in library and information science in four Indian states.
- To study the LIS job advertisements State Wise.
- To assess comparative study of advertisement published in four Indian states.
- To present the current status of job opportunities in Library and Information Science Profession.

Research Methodology

The main objective of this study is to analyse the library job advertisements in Four states of India to understand the nature and conditions of the job requirements. Data for this study was used from Job Advertisements published from Employments news, university news and LIS links from year 2012 to 2017.

Most of advertisements are downloaded from these sources or their reference were noted down. The data entry is done in MS Access and further the data has been tabulated and graphs have been prepared using MS-Excel and these data has been analysed to come upon generalised findings and a meaningful conclusion is drawn.

Name of State	Employment News	University News	LIS Link	Total	% Percentage
Maharashtra	20	398	245	663	50.03%
Madhya Pradesh	42	09	156	207	15.62%
Gujrat	28	18	171	217	16.37%
Karnataka	24	05	209	238	17.96%
Total	114	430	781	1325	100%

Table 1.1: States wise Distribution of LIS Job Opportunities**Figure 1.1: States wise Distribution of LIS Job Opportunities**

The state-wise distribution of the LIS job opportunities given in table 1.1 shows that Maharashtra produces the highest i.e. 50.03% (663) LIS job opportunities followed by Karnataka 17.96% (238). Gujrat produces 16.37% (217) job opportunities while Madhya Pradesh produces 15.62% (207) job opportunities. From this four Indian states Maharashtra produces maximum LIS jobs opportunities generated during the period from 2012 to 2017.

Maharashtra is imperative state for the point of view of LIS jobs where most of the LIS jobs create in academic libraries of various educational institutions. Karnataka also among the major states that accommodate LIS professionals. The analysis in table 1.1 and figure 1.1 indicate that in almost every state has LIS job opportunities, this confirms a wide scope in the LIS field for the future job aspirants. It may also be a piece of good news for the LIS job aspirants who are not aware of where to look for better job searches. The analysis can also be utilized to set or revised the career objectives of the LIS job aspirants.

Conclusion:

This comparative study examined the status of job opportunities in librarianship across four Indian states: Maharashtra, Karnataka, Gujarat, and Madhya Pradesh duration from 2012 to 2017. The findings reveal significant variations in the availability of job opportunities across these states.

Maharashtra indicates highest job opportunities of the total job opportunities in librarianship, indicating a strong demand for librarians in this state. Karnataka is the second highest from these four states for LIS job opportunities. Gujarat is followed by Karnataka for LIS job opportunities. Madhya Pradesh indicates very less job opportunities as compared to all four states respectively.

These findings suggest that librarianship job market is skewed in Favor of Maharashtra, with limited opportunities available in the other three states. The study's findings have implications for library administrators, and librarians to address the disparities in job opportunities, may need to develop targeted initiatives to promote

librarianship in Karnataka, Gujarat, and Madhya Pradesh. Library administrators can focus on developing strategies to attract and retain librarians in these states. Librarians, on the other hand, may need to consider acquiring specialized skills or certifications to enhance their employability in a competitive job market. The future of LIS professionals is bright and library profession sector would give more job avenues to the fresh library science graduates, post-graduates, and certificate, diploma degree holders in the coming years to come. There would be also more job avenues in the higher educational institutions like colleges, technical institutions, colleges and universities for higher as well as lower-level posts.

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